

TRITIUM: AN EXCELLENT TRACER IN HYDROLOGY

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ABSTRACT: Tritium (³H) is a radioactive isotope of hydrogen with a half-life of 12.32 years. It is produced in the upper atmosphere in nuclear reactions of mainly secondary neutrons and nitrogen nuclei. After its production, ³H enters the water cycle. Due to the thermonuclear weapon tests in the 50's and 60's, a huge amount of man-made tritium was injected into the atmosphere providing a global tracer experiment in the hydrology. The so-called bomb-peak of 1963 can be seen everywhere in the planet. This artificial ³H-excess is the base of ³H/³He dating, which can be used in shallow groundwater hydrology. As a recent discovery, the production rate as well as the concentration of tritium in precipitation are modulated by the solar cycle. This variation can be also observed in continental ice layers. Studying old ice layers before the nuclear are, the natural level of tritium can be studied. The variation of tritium has been now embedded in atmospheric general circulation models. The presentation gives an overview how tritium is spatially and temporarily distributed in the components of the water cycle. Examples of ³H/³He dating in karst hydrology and the calculation of recharge rates will be also provided.

Key words: Tritium, tracer, the water cycle, ³H-excess, ³H/³He dating

